

COLLABORATIVE MOBILE LEARNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the analysis of various approaches to the concepts of "mobile learning" and "collaborative learning" separately and then together, which forms the basis of modern innovative approaches and teaching methods. The paper presents the characteristic features of mobile learning and collaborative learning, and also analyzes their innovative symbiosis - collaborative mobile learning. Based on the definition of the concept of "mobile learning", the concepts of "didactic information and communication technology" and "mobile collaborative learning model" are identified and formulated.

Introduction

In the modern world, various newspapers, websites, international forums, conferences and publications daily report on numerous "innovations" that are supposed to improve our lives, make the economy more dynamic, and reduce unemployment. The world of education has not been spared "innovations" that are supposed to allow everyone to learn using digital networks. When we talk about teaching young people in this way, the first thing that comes to mind is the educational process through mobile phones, tablets, laptops, etc., which is the technological basis for distance, online learning not only individually, but also in a group, plenary way, that is, cooperatively. However, studies have shown that learning in digital networks one-on-one with a computer or mobile devices is very difficult and not possible for everyone. Can collaboration and cooperation become auxiliary means? What exactly is the contribution to educational innovations and how can they make it? I offer a critical semantic reflection of various terms that exist in this area, from the point of view of my own research work and practice. Successful completion of learning in digital networks requires a range of competencies and abilities that not all pupils and students possess. Among them, the ability to work together is in demand, as it is an element that facilitates learning. By clarifying the meaning and critically analyzing the different types of interaction and collaboration in learning, we try to understand the aspects that distinguish them and those that can possibly lead to educational innovations.

Main part

What is mobile e-learning? Mobile E-learning, or learning through electronic means,

such as mobile gadgets, androids can be characterized from several points of view: economic, organizational, educational, technological. In the formulation of modern educational trends, "e-learning is "the use of new multimedia Internet technologies to improve the quality of learning: on the one hand, by facilitating access to resources and services; on the other, by exchanging and collaborating at a distance"¹. Numerous data coming from the North American continent indicate that e-learning is similar to a combination of existing educational practices and educational technologies, the development of which is conditioned by the development of the Internet. Moreover, as recent developments have shown, in the process of its development, e-learning is acquiring characteristics that are technologically different from the educational technologies known to us. This technological side of learning (dissemination of content, accessibility of the route) seems to be predominant in this educational model. Although some of its aspects are related to pedagogy, I see a shortcoming in the fact that pedagogy is actually lacking a relationship to the e-learning system, which looks more like a "poor relative" and within which the educational process is more techno-centric than pedagogic.

An analysis of domestic and foreign pedagogical research devoted to the definition of the concept of "mobile learning" shows that today there are various approaches to its definition and there is a significant number of corresponding definitions. Analyzing the concept of "mobile learning" presented on authoritative foreign Internet portals, Yu. Dukhnich gives a number of definitions of this concept:

- mobile learning is any activity that allows people to be more productive in such processes as consuming and creating information, as well as any interaction with it, using a compact digital device that a person uses regularly. Such a device should provide reliable communication and fit in a pocket (eLearning Guild)
- mobile learning is the use of common technologies, including wireless networks and mobile networks, to facilitate, support, enrich learning and provide greater learning reach
- mobile learning is any learning that occurs in a setting where the learner is not in a fixed, predetermined location, or learning in which a person takes advantage of the learning opportunities and benefits of mobile technologies.

Now let's move to the term "collaborative learning", in order to thoroughly understand this innovative and interactive learning method yet separately from mobile learning and then deduce these two concepts in one learning approach. Collaborative learning can be seen as a philosophy of interaction and a way of life where people are responsible for their actions, including their learning, and respect the capabilities and contributions of their partners. Collaborative learning "is a way of learning in which the learner learns through interaction with peers." The educational outcome of the learner's individual work in constructing his or her knowledge is supported by the activities of the group and team. The learner shares resources with the group, uses group work to learn. The structure of the activity is flexible and open, and the route of exploration and discovery is free. The teacher plays the role of a facilitator in learning, while the group acts as a source of information, motivation, as a means of self-help and mutual support, and as a special place of interaction for the collective construction of knowledge. In collaborative learning, there is no a priori distribution of roles, as in simple joint (cooperative) work. Individuals gradually merge with the group, which

becomes a single whole and whose potential is greater than the sum of its parts, which often allows for high-quality work. At the same time, there is both the responsibility of each individual for the common cause and the responsibility of the team as a whole. All members of the group maintain close and constant contact, each brings his or her own action to the group, each can contribute to the work of other members of the group in order to increase productivity and thus join the principle of continuous improvement in the performance of each task and the project as a whole. The interaction of group members is long-term, and it is the coordination of the team that helps in achieving the final goal. For greater coordination between members of the group, the number of its participants should not exceed five people.

Often, when adult learners, sometimes teachers, hear the term collaborative learning, it is automatically associated with the negative context of working in a group, from which they had to suffer in the school environment or in the workplace. They refer to their own, sometimes unpleasant experiences, which makes them want to abandon the concept of collaboration, which they regard as unrealizable or as an attempt to shift the burden of learning from the teacher to the students. In open distance learning, we must explain well the benefits of collaborative work and the need to support each of its participants, especially in terms of motivational dynamics, where the external aspect is an essential variable in building success. This initial anxiety of some students is worth noting, since it represents an example of misunderstanding of what has become an absolutely indispensable approach to the greatest viability of teaching and learning in digital networks.

In my opinion, collaborative mobile learning should be based on the following principles:

- the results of joint work provide mutual understanding, possibly greater than when working independently from each other, and the use of mobile devices should not affect the remote distance from each other in any way, since mobile learning has audio and video opportunities for fruitful collaboration and cooperation within a study group or class with a teacher;
- oral and written interactions contribute to better understanding;
- the ability to realize through lived experience the relationships that exist between social interaction and better mutual understanding;
- some elements of this deep understanding are unique and unpredictable;
- participation is voluntary and should provide freedom, but at the same time be strongly supported.

It seems that the collaborative learning mode requires a broader participation of stakeholders. For a group, this ability to develop its human capital is considered by some as a sign of collective intelligence.

Conclusion.

The appliance of new learning tools, the reorganization of courses, the provision of greater freedom to learners, the expansion of the range of possibilities – all this cannot be systematically defined as innovation in collaborative mobile learning. It is the result of the exploration of the unknown, which eventually becomes visible and understandable for the benefit of many. Innovation should not become trivial to such an extent that every new activity, every new product, every ordinary or unusual technology can be deliberately embellished with “innovation”. Cooperative and collaborative types of learning are additive

and complementary forms that make pedagogical sense, but do not, in my opinion, provide innovative breakthroughs.

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INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY